

Biomarker and AI-supported FX06 therapy to prevent progression from mild and moderate to severe stages of COVID-19

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Abstract

About 14% of COVID-19 patients with mild or moderate disease develop severe symptoms and are eventually admitted to the intensive care unit. The main goal of the COVend project is to reduce the number of COVID-19 patients in hospitals and thereby reduce the burden on patients and their families, hospital staff, and the healthcare sector. The specific objectives are, first, to enrich the current portfolio of SARS-CoV-2/COVID-19 prophylactics and therapeutics by clinically testing FX06 as a promising drug candidate. Second, to provide effective therapy against SARS-CoV-2 by using innovative immune biomarker profiling, endothelial cell assessment methods, and artificial intelligence-driven models for decision support for clinical treatment of COVID19 disease. This is expected to prevent a progression to severe disease and subsequent hospitalisation.

Endothelial cells are the main regulators of vascular homeostasis (dynamic equilibrium), as they interact with both circulating cells and cells present in the vessel wall. When endothelial function deteriorates, vascular homeostasis is impaired, leading to increased permeability for blood and its components as well as inflammation of the endothelium. FX06 has shown to have a protective effect on the endothelium by reducing the inflammatory process. This way, the disease progress will be interrupted, resulting in faster recovery of the patients and less admissions to intensive care units

Table of Contents

Partner short names	4
Abbreviations.....	4
Revision history.....	4
Executive Summary.....	5
1. Key facts.....	6
2. Aims and objectives.....	6
3. Strategy.....	6
4. Technical implementation	7
4.1. WordPress	7
4.2. Website structure	7
4.2.1. Homepage.....	7
4.2.2. About the project.....	7
4.2.3. Technologies	10
4.2.4. Team	10
4.2.5. Information.....	11
4.2.6. News	12
5. Outlook.....	12

Partner short names

GUF	Johann Wolfgang Goethe Universität Frankfurt am Main
accelCH	accelopment Schweiz AG
ESAIC	European Society of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care
F-ITMP	Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology ITMP
F4	F4 Pharma GmbH
TAU	Tampereen Korkeakoulusaatio SR
UCD	University College Dublin
UMCG	Universitair Medisch Centrum Groningen
MiDA	Medical Intelligent Data Analytics GmbH
UHW	University Hospital Würzburg
ASST	ASST Fatebenefratelli Sacco – Luigi Sacco Hospital
UNIPG	Università degli Studi di Perugia
KC	Lietuvos Sveikatos Mokslu Universiteto Ligonine Kauno Klinikos
ICS-HUB	Hospital Universitari de Bellvitge
UMFCD	Universitatea de Medicina si Farmacie Carol Davila din Bucuresti
CHUC	Centro Hospitalar e Universitario de Coimbra E.P.E.
APHP	Assistance Publique – Hôpitaux de Paris

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
HEU	Horizon Europe
M	Month
MS	Milestone
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union

Revision history

Date	Authors	Revision
24.09.2021	Kevin Keyaert (accelCH)	Draft version
28.09.2021	Andreia Cruz (accelCH)	Revision 1
30.09.2021	Benjamin Ginski (GUF), Regina Minazhetdinova (GUF)	Final version

Executive Summary

The deliverable D8.1 - **COVend website**, presents the COVend project website, describing the main structure of the website, how it is set up and how it will be maintained throughout the project's duration and for the five years following its completion. The project website serves as a powerful tool to communicate, inform and raise awareness on the endeavours and progress of the project, enabling the COVend consortium to easily reach out to all its stakeholders. Tailored to the COVend stakeholders, the website provides up-to-date, consistent and comprehensive information on the project.

1. Key facts

The COVend website has the main purpose of raising awareness of the project's endeavours as well as to function as a central online portal to disseminate its results to the scientific community and to communicate its outcomes to the general public and wider audience of non-experts.

Key facts are:

- The COVend website address is www.covend-project.eu;
- The website was first launched on 1 August 2021 (Month 1);
- accelCH created and currently maintains the website using WordPress;
- The project website is securely hosted on accelCH's webserver.

2. Aims and objectives

The main aims of the project website are to raise awareness of the COVend project and its network, to maintain an open and wide-reaching means of communication with the COVend stakeholder groups and to keep an updated platform informing on the most current project developments, key results and outcomes.

The specific objectives are to not only provide a source of information, but to also create an interactive platform for exchange with the various stakeholder groups including the scientific and healthcare communities as well as the general public and project's own network. This is achieved by including engaging audio-visual material that clearly and effectively communicates the project vision, endeavours and results to a wide public and by providing educational material, news, and continuously updated content.

3. Strategy

The website functions as a focal point for all stakeholder groups to find information on the partners involved in the project, on the technological and scientific details behind the research being conducted and all updates concerning the project progress as well as events and key achievements.

The COVend website aims to keep all its stakeholder groups involved and interested in the project throughout its entire duration. This will be achieved by prompt communication of the project's newest results, regular and timely updates on news and events and the enhancement of engagement opportunities through event registration functions, when appropriate.

All of the website functionality is provided in an intuitive and user-friendly manner. Moreover, it has a responsive design, i.e. an adapted interface when viewed on mobile devices or tablets, which makes it easy to navigate on a small screen and guarantees convenient access to the website from any device.

4. Technical implementation

The COVend website created with WordPress is implemented in a way that allows easy maintenance and provides an appealing experience to its users.

4.1. WordPress

The website was created with the online website design tool [WordPress](#). This tool offers flexible and professional layouts, a user-friendly interface for ease of editing and numerous additional plugins to integrate interactive features and adjust the website to the project's needs. As a default feature, WordPress offers responsive designs, i.e. website layouts that adapt to different screen sizes. Posts are displayed in reverse chronological order, so that the most recent news entry is shown at the top of the page and on the COVend website's homepage.

4.2. Website structure

The website is currently structured as described in the following sub-sections, in line with the strategy, aims and objectives described above. However, this structure and the individual web pages are subject to change over time and will be adapted as the project develops, notably to include the Results page. The main navigation menu allows the viewer to easily reach the key pages of the website, currently including 'About', 'Therapy', 'Technologies', 'Team', 'Information' and 'News'. The EU flag and acknowledgement both are displayed below the banner image of the homepage and a footer displayed on all pages includes the copyright and links to 'Contact', 'Cookie Policy' and 'Privacy Policy'.

4.2.1. Homepage

The [homepage](#) is the landing page for first time access to the website through entering the URL ([covend-project.eu](#)) in an internet browser (e.g., Firefox), a search engine (e.g., Google) or through a link on a different website (e.g., partner websites) (see Figure 1). When browsing through the COVend website, users can easily return to the homepage by clicking on the COVend logo in the header, as is common practice for many modern websites.

The homepage enables the viewer to immediately gather an overview of the project, through an opening summary of the project, a news section, contact information from the project coordinator, and an overview of the COVend partners. The homepage is well linked to all its other current pages, where the viewer can find more information on the project, the research conducted and the latest news and events. When new pages will be added to the main navigation menu, care will be taken to link these within the homepage main text as well.

4.2.2. About the project

When hovering over the 'About' main navigation menu item, its submenu with the two related pages 'Objectives', and 'Work plan' is accessible.

[Objectives](#) lists the principal goals that COVend aims to fulfil. The page can be reached via the corresponding item in the navigation menu (see Figure 2).

[Work plan](#) provides a schematic overview of the various work packages with their descriptions and lead partner. The top image describes how the work packages are interrelated (see Figure 3).

Figure 1: Homepage view of the COVend website

Figure 2: Overview of the 'Objectives' page of the COVend website accessible in the submenu of the key menu 'About'

Work plan

WP1 will be coordinated and managed by EU1 and supported by executive committees and local members. WP1 will ensure that COVend's objectives are achieved and the collaboration with other initiatives is added value to the project. WP2 and WP3 focus on the preparation and the testing of the emerging therapeutic candidates (TC). WP4, WP5 and WP6 are complementary to that they develop tools to determine specific risk conditions to behaviour and AI based predictive models for drugs on supports to prove or disprove the benefits of FDCs and the role of an individual patient therapy. WP7 will evaluate the safety risks and the efficacy of the candidates and the social and economic implications of the new therapies. Finally, WP8 will ensure proper dissemination of project results to target and non-target populations, researchers, healthcare providers, patients, patient advocacy groups and policy makers.

WP1: Project management and collaboration with other initiatives
Lead: EU1, Co-Lead: EU2, EU3, EU4

WP2: FDCs preparation for clinical trials (CMC, Chemistry, manufacturing & control)
Lead: TA, Co-Lead: GUP

WP3: Management and implementation of therapeutic clinical trial
Lead: GUP, Co-Lead: EU1, EU2, EU3, EU4

WP4: Immuno character profiling
Lead: EU1, EU2, EU3, EU4

WP5: Embryonic cell assessment
Lead: EU1, EU2, EU3, EU4

WP6: Decision support models
Lead: EU1, EU2, EU3, EU4

WP7: Socio-economic impact and cost effectiveness analyses (CEA)
Lead: EU1, EU2, EU3, EU4

WP8: Communication, dissemination and registration
Lead: EU1, EU2, EU3, EU4

WP9: Ethics requirements
Lead: GUP

- WP1: Project management and collaboration with other initiatives +
- WP2: FDCs preparation for clinical trials (CMC, Chemistry, manufacturing & control) +
- WP3: Management and implementation of therapeutic clinical trial +
- WP4: Immuno character profiling +
- WP5: Embryonic cell assessment +
- WP6: Decision support models +
- WP7: Socio-economic impact and cost effectiveness analyses (CEA) +
- WP8: Communication, dissemination and registration +
- WP9: Ethics requirements +

Figure 3: Overview of the ‘Work plan’ of the COVend website accessible in the submenu of the key menu ‘About’

Therapy

Although the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has shaped our daily life for over a year, there is no causal therapy currently available. Still today, the therapy is limited to symptom control. Consequently, great expectations are placed on the various vaccines.

However, the public often forgets that vaccines can lose their effectiveness due to viral mutations, such as prominent Delta variant. It is therefore essential to develop drugs that can reliably prevent severe courses of COVID-19. To date, there are no genuinely effective therapies for COVID-19 nor antivirals against the virus that causes the disease SARS-CoV-2. Although, some treatments have shown some benefits in certain subpopulations of patients or for certain end-points.

Researchers and manufacturers are conducting large-scale clinical trials to evaluate various therapies for COVID-19. Due to the varying stages of the disease, it is likely that two-stage methods will be used. Therapeutic approaches which in the very early phases antiviral drugs and antibodies might be best for fighting the virus, advanced stages are characterized more by the host response. Hence, drugs are needed that interfere with the host response that is directly or indirectly induced by the virus.

As the underlying pathological disease process of COVID-19 is characterized by a continuous progression of endothelial injury, FDCs, a protective substance against endothelial damage, is expected to prevent the disease from progressing from a moderate to a severe stage. To prove this hypothesis, which is well based on experimental animal data, we propose a controlled, randomized, placebo-controlled study in approximately 300 patients with mild to moderate COVID-19.

Key Messages

- COVID-19 is a disease that patients will be living with for a long time, and it is important to develop effective therapies.
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Figure 4: Overview of the ‘Therapy’ page which is one of the key pages accessible on the Homepage

4.2.3. Technologies

The ‘Technologies’ page provides an overview of the tools and technologies that COVend will deploy to map and analyse the impact of the therapy that is being researched (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Overview of the ‘Technologies’ page which is one of the key pages accessible on the Homepage

4.2.4. Team

The [Team](#) page provides a listing of all partners and their staff forming the COVend consortium, with a map depicting the locations in Europe where these partners are based. The picture below is a partial screenshot of this listing (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Overview of the ‘Team’ page which is one of the key pages accessible on the Homepage

4.2.6. News

The [News](#) page publishes the news items coming out of the COVend project (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Overview of the ‘News’ page which is one of the key pages accessible on the Homepage

5. Outlook

The next steps in the development of the COVend website will involve populating webpages about the COVend consortium with partner-specific descriptions and pictures of staff involved in the project. The various partners have already been asked to contribute with their content.

Day-to-day activities will require updating the website with news and results. As the project progresses, a dedicated webpage will be created to accommodate for the corresponding deliverables and reports.